

GOALS AND OBJECTIVES OF DEVELOPING READING AND WRITING SKILLS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14895852>

Abstract. *Ensuring the implementation of the child's right to education, preserving and strengthening the child's physical, mental and spiritual development, as well as ensuring the child's adaptation to society and readiness to continue education in general education institutions are the main goals of preschool educational organizations. The article discusses the goals and tasks of teaching literacy in preparatory groups.*

Keywords. *literacy, skills, skills, school education, areas of development, didactic game, reading skills, writing skills.*

It is no exaggeration to say that since 2017, under the leadership of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, the focus of state social policy on preschool education has begun a period of radical changes in this area. Our Head of State consistently analyzed the problems and shortcomings in the field of preschool education, including the fact that the number of state-owned preschool educational organizations has decreased by more than 47 percent, the material and technical base of existing educational organizations does not meet modern requirements, and the fact that the staff working in preschool educational organizations have secondary specialized education, so the training in school preparatory groups is not sufficient and does not meet modern requirements, and especially the low coverage of children was emphasized.

At a meeting held on August 16, 2017 under the chairmanship of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, the issues of strengthening the national gene pool in our country, raising the younger generation as mature personnel were thoroughly analyzed, and many areas of development of the education system were identified. In particular, the tasks of radically reforming the preschool education system in terms of structure and increasing the coverage of children in preschool educational organizations were outlined. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically improve the management of the preschool education system" dated September 30, 2017 and the Resolution No. PQ-3305 "On the organization of the activities of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan", all aspects of the comprehensive development of the preschool education system,

raising children in a healthy and harmonious way, and improving the quality of their preparation for school education were identified.

In order to eliminate the above-mentioned shortcomings and problems, further improve the preschool education system, ensure equal access of children to quality preschool education, and develop the non-state sector of preschool education services, the “Concept for the Development of the Preschool Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” was approved.

Preparing children for school implies, firstly, organizing educational work in preschool educational organizations in such a way as to ensure a high level of general, comprehensive development of school-age children; secondly, providing special preparation for children to master the subjects that they must master in the primary grades of school.

The main goal of literacy training in preschool educational organizations is to create the basis for the formation of a functionally literate person, to ensure the development of the child's language and speech, and to help them understand that their native language is

The main tasks of the literacy period:

- teaching children to read and write, giving them basic information about speech, language, literature;
- expanding children's worldview;
- activating internal and external (oral and written) speech;
- developing intellectual and cognitive activity, forming a positive attitude towards reading in a child;
- developing psychophysiological functions necessary for effective learning to read and write.

Both reading and writing are complex speech activities. These processes are an important factor in the development of memory, attention, speech, thinking and perception of preschool children, taking into account their age characteristics. Therefore, when teaching preschool children to read, educators should pay attention to the following:

1. While reading, the child sees one letter, brings pictures to mind to recognize it, remembers pictures or other letters, and when he remembers it, he is eager to say it, but the educator does not let him say it, requiring him to say the syllable. Until the child remembers the second letter, the first one is forgotten or they combine them to form a syllable, and the reading process slows down.

2. Often the child loses the line he is reading, has to reread the letter, syllable, or word. As the child's attention expands, he begins to perceive the syllable and word as a whole.

3. A child who is just learning to read does not understand the content of the text he is reading, because he gives a lot of effort to how to read the word. The teacher's questions, visual, multimedia materials and didactic games ensure their conscious reading.

4. An inexperienced reader finds a word by looking at the first syllable or picture. This leads to reading errors. To prevent such errors, words are taught syllable by syllable, attention is paid to analyzing the word from the syllable-sound side, and analyzing and synthesizing it from the sound-letter side.

In order for preschool children to successfully master reading, great attention should be paid to developing their perception, memory, thinking, and speech. In teaching literacy, it is important to develop phonemic hearing skills, that is, to teach them to pronounce sounds clearly, distinguish them from other sounds, and develop the ability to distinguish that sound from a syllable or word.

Phonemic hearing is an important condition for developing spelling skills. Therefore, during the period of teaching literacy, it is advisable to use special exercises, educational games, and interesting tasks to develop auditory perception in children.

In the writing process, children should remember how to hold a pen correctly, how to place a notebook correctly, how to move their hand along the lines of the notebook when writing a letter, and how to write a letter in a block letter in the intended cell. This process tires children mentally and physically, especially their finger and shoulder muscles. That is why it is important to spend physical moments in the activity.

In the process of writing, the child moves the pen (pencil) slowly, hesitantly on the paper, stops writing a letter and compares it with the sample, sometimes goes out of line, paints over and corrects mistakes. In this case, he turns to the educator every minute, his hand and head work together when writing.

The writing process also requires conscious actions from the children. Therefore, it is very important for the educator to pay great attention to the child's actions with patience and satisfaction during the writing process.

The main task of teaching preschool children to read is to form correct, conscious, expressive reading skills by introducing children to sounds and letters, teaching them their correct pronunciation. Also, enriching children's vocabulary, cultivating coherent speech, forming a system of knowledge, developing hearing, perceptiveness are also important during the period of teaching literacy. Because the effectiveness of a child's education in primary school largely depends on his knowledge of his native language and how developed his speech is. In conclusion,

the child's acquisition of reading skills by the time he enters grade 1 should be recognized as his achievements in the field of "early development". If a child has such skills and abilities, he will have the opportunity to independently read and study materials in various academic subjects. On the contrary, a child's lack of sufficient mastery of reading skills can lead to his or her development falling behind and his or her inability to actively master new elements of learning and cognitive activity.

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